

Autonomous agents for Hyper-distributed applications: a role-based approach for the Swarm

Francesc Lordan^a, Xavier Casas-Moreno^a, Philip Cummins^a, Javier Conejero^a, Rosa M. Badia^a, Raül Sirvent^a

^aBarcelona Supercomputing Center - Centro Nacional de Supercomputación, Barcelona, Spain

Abstract

Hyper-distributed applications leverage the Compute Continuum to offer highly-available, trustworthy and secure services with low latency. However, given the number of managed devices and their heterogeneity, finding an optimal distribution of these application's functionalities is a challenging problem tackled either manually or with a resource-hungry, centralized solution. This article proposes a ground-breaking programming environment where applications are composed of multiple cooperative roles to be executed by the devices. A novel software stack transforms each device into an Autonomous ageNT (ANT) able to decide which roles it executes, according to its capabilities and context, and enabling the construction of a cooperative, self-organized platform.

In this article, we present the COLMENA framework and the programming model that defines a service as a set of roles, behaviors, and abstractions, leveraging declarative programming. We present the architecture design and current implementation of the building blocks of the COLMENA software stack. Using a custom-built simulator, we compare different policies for role selection, including rule-based and reinforcement learning approaches. Finally, we demonstrate the validity of the programming model and the middleware by deploying a pilot use-case over an infrastructure of heterogeneous hardware devices and show reactivity towards the events of adding and removing devices in the platform.

Keywords: Swarm, Edge, Cloud, Compute Continuum, Distributed System, Programming Model, Decentralized Platform, Autonomous Agent

1. Introduction

Recent advancements in Cloud Computing have enabled the widespread deployment and accessibility of distributed applications. Although IoT devices are extensively used for data collection, nearly 80% of data processing still takes place in centralized computing facilities and data centers [1]. The Cloud Computing paradigm relies heavily on the network infrastructure, which introduces higher communication latency and significant energy consumption, while leaving computational resources available at the edge largely under-exploited. Such dependence on centralized infrastructures poses a significant barrier to achieving climate-neutrality and sustainable societal goals.

Hyper-distributed applications, which integrate data and resources from multi-tenant, geographically dispersed infrastructures interconnected by heterogeneous

and often unreliable networks, demand low latencies to ensure high availability, trust, and security [2]. The Compute Continuum addresses these challenges by unifying Edge and Cloud resources into a cohesive computing platform [3]. This platform harnesses the capabilities of IoT, Edge, and Far-Edge devices, thereby minimizing reliance on Cloud infrastructures and network stability. By doing so, it enhances the responsiveness, accuracy, and energy efficiency of IT systems. However, the challenge of defining and deploying applications across the Continuum while minimizing human intervention remains an open research topic.

Swarm Computing is an emerging paradigm applicable to the Compute Continuum characterized by the collaboration of multiple autonomous agents operating in a fully decentralized manner to achieve a shared global objective. Swarm Computing offers numerous advantages. By exploiting data locality, the Continuum strengthens the security and privacy of the services and enhances their energy and resource usage effi-

Email addresses: francesc.lordan@bsc.es (Francesc Lordan), xavier.casas@bsc.es (Xavier Casas-Moreno)

ciency, thus, reducing operational costs. Its lower communication latencies enable higher-performance solutions. Furthermore, the decentralization of the control plane provided by Swarm technologies significantly improves the scalability and fault tolerance of applications. The adoption of the Continuum and Swarm technologies is anticipated to positively influence stakeholders involved in all the stages of the life-cycle of a hyper-distributed application: construction (Developers), deployment (Service Providers and Infrastructure Owners), operation (Service Providers, Infrastructure Owners and end-users) and maintenance (Developers).

The novelty of these concepts, coupled with the lack of supporting tools for stakeholders, poses a major barrier to the widespread adoption of these technologies. Current hyper-distributed applications are predominantly custom-built and highly specialized. The vast heterogeneity and extreme scale of the infrastructure, encompassing both computing devices and networks, significantly complicates the management of the Continuum and the orchestration of applications. This complexity is further exacerbated by the dynamic nature of the Continuum. For example, devices joining or leaving the infrastructure, unreliable networks, and workloads driven by fluctuating user demands, introduce additional layers of unpredictability and challenges to efficient operation. Automatically optimizing the management of this complex ecosystem often requires resource-intensive solutions. For simplicity, these solutions are typically centralized in the Cloud, which undermines the decentralized potential of the Continuum.

Moreover, this management complexity often permeates service development. Hyper-distributed applications typically consist of numerous sub-services, often encapsulated within virtual environments such as containers, which combine data processing components with communication solutions to integrate them. The choice of technologies and solutions for these components is usually driven by a predefined deployment strategy taking the infrastructure's characteristics into account. However, these strategies are predominantly static, giving priority to management simplicity over flexibility. As a result, hyper-distributed applications struggle to adapt in a dynamic and evolving environment, which negatively impacts their performance, efficiency, and cost.

The work presented in this article embraces this paradigm shift toward the Swarm by introducing COLMENA¹: an open framework designed to develop,

deploy and operate hyper-distributed applications on large, heterogeneous, and dynamic groups of devices across the Continuum.

To simplify the development and maintenance of hyper-distributed applications targeting swarms, the framework includes a programming model that allows developers to describe application logic as a composite of interacting roles. Each role is defined by its functionality or behavior (program logic) and a set of hardware requirements. This abstraction enables developers to concentrate on the functionality of the application, leaving the complexities of low-level infrastructure management to the underlying runtime system.

For distributing and running these roles, each infrastructure component - whether a hardware node, virtual environment, or entire virtualization platform - hosts a lightweight, energy-efficient software known as the COLMENA Agent. This software endows devices with the intelligence to become self-aware of their capabilities and context and transforms the device into an Autonomous agent (ANT). By hosting the COLMENA Agent, ANTs can self-organize to form a flexible, agile, secure and fully decentralized platform with a mesh architecture: the COLMENA platform.

The platform effectively integrates diverse device capabilities — including computing, storage, connectivity, and cyber-physical functions — into a unified ecosystem that promotes a seamless collaboration among devices through inter-device communication, data sharing, and computational workload exchange. This integration operates transparently across various providers, network zones, and connectivity types.

The COLMENA Agent software running on each ANT drives the distribution of roles by dynamically selecting which roles are executed locally, based on the ANT's capabilities, current context, and the roles' requirements. This process is further guided by application-specific indicators such as expected performance, energy consumption, and quality of service (QoS) and experience (QoE), compared to those currently delivered. By enabling distributed, autonomous decision-making, COLMENA eliminates the need for resource-intensive, centralized management mechanisms, paving the way for extreme-scale elastic and heterogeneous systems. Besides, it enhances the robustness and efficiency of applications with the flexibility to quickly react to infrastructure or workload changes by dynamically reassigning the roles played by each ANT with zero setup and reconfiguration effort for the operator.

This article continues by providing an overview of the state of the art of the related fields of knowledge

¹<https://proyecto-colmena.com/>

and contributes to it by **i)** describing a **pilot use case**, offering a practical context for COLMENA, **ii)** detailing a **software stack**, which forms the backbone of the framework, **iii)** specifying a syntax for **the programming model**, **iv)** proposing some **decision-making policies** for ANTs, empowering them to autonomously select roles for local execution and achieve the desired collective behavior., **v)** providing a **single-node multi-thread simulator** capable of emulating the behavior of the platform for testing and validation purposes, **vi)** **evaluating the proposed policies** using the simulator to assess their effectiveness and impact, **vii)** building and integrating those components of the software stack to deliver a minimal-viability **prototype** of the COLMENA framework, **viii)** and demonstrating the viability of the proposal **running the pilot use case** using the developed prototype.

This article, along with the COLMENA framework, contributes to the definition of next-generation computing and data technologies by easing the programming, deployment and maintenance of hyper-distributed applications on the Continuum. To enhance the trust of end-users in these systems, COLMENA aims at keeping a transparent and comprehensible operation, open to the adoption of new generations of hardware (processors, network or smart systems) and, thus, improve the interoperability of the system and avoid vendor lock-in.

2. Related work

The orchestration of services in the Cloud is often achieved through the use of Cloud Operating Systems (OS) that manage the creation of multiple Cloud environments, as well as the deployment and operation of services as compositions of virtual entities. Vendor-proprietary solutions are the most well-known examples (Amazon Web Services, Google Cloud Platform, and Microsoft Azure). Still, there are also open-source, interoperable solutions such as OpenStack² and OpenNebula³. Due to its popularity, Kubernetes⁴ (K8s) is a widespread solution supported by most Cloud OSs to orchestrate containers in clusters. To the best of our knowledge, all these solutions heavily rely on a centralized architecture to manage both the infrastructure and the virtual environments.

The Edge presents a heterogeneous scenario with constrained resources and unstable networking. Some

lightweight implementations of Kubernetes (e.g., K3s) focus on the resource constraints issue. Frameworks like Cilium⁵, Skupper⁶ and Clusterlink [4] provide networking and security functionalities to Kubernetes edge clusters. However, the Edge demands a decentralized management solution for not remaining a surrogate of the Cloud. Some projects are already working in that direction. PiCasso [5] combines virtual environments with decentralized community mesh networks. OpenWhisk⁷, Colony [6] or Serverledge [7] provide the execution of serverless functions (FaaS) in the Edge.

Developing services deployed across the Continuum is based on tailored solutions where data is collected (and often preprocessed) on the Edge and then sent to the Cloud for archiving or analysis using publish-subscribe standards (e.g., MQTT), Apache Kafka or Remote Procedure Call (RPC) for synchronous communication. Data management systems proposed for IoT [8]⁸ support the fast ingestion and analysis of time series in the Cloud, requiring continuous data transfers to and from edge devices, thus disabling fast responses and the flexibility required by swarms. Other solutions [9]⁹ focus on resource heterogeneity combined with restrictions, avoiding data transfers to and from the Cloud, but assuming fixed infrastructures. The fully decentralized nature of swarms requires new approaches for managing and processing data. For instance, dataClay [10] is an object-based data storage solution optimized for dynamic environments.

Another way of defining distributed applications in the Continuum is by using programming models. Traditional programming models for distributed systems—such as data analytics frameworks [11, 12] and general-purpose workflow managers [13, 14]—have centralized global orchestrators. Another common paradigm for developing concurrent and distributed systems is the actor model, where an application can be defined as a composition of standalone actors communicating among them. Erlang [15] and Akka [16] implement the actor model, but their runtime systems are not prepared to face the challenges set by the continuum.

Programming models targeting swarms (e.g., Buzz [17]) have focused on designing simple reactive controllers, neural networks, state machines, or behavior trees for individual devices that give rise to desired swarm behaviors [18, 19, 20]. Mandrake [21]

²<https://www.openstack.org/>

³<https://opennebula.io/>

⁴<https://kubernetes.io/>

⁵<https://cilium.io/>

⁶<https://skupper.io/>

⁷<https://openwhisk.apache.org/>

⁸BWorld Robot Control Software. <https://www.influxdata.com>

⁹ExtremeDB <https://www.mobject.com/extremedbfamily>

proposes a programming model to define decentralized applications that deal with autonomous agents built on Protocols Over Things [22]. However, unlike COLMENA, Mandrake and Buzz have not been applied to the Continuum nor considered the dynamic allocation of roles on autonomous devices. In the literature, role assignment in multi-agent systems (allocation of items between different entities) is typically solved in a centralized manner by running classical optimization algorithms [23, 24, 25]. There are attempts for a distributed allocation, which are market-based and built on contract net protocol. Discovering controllers for individuals that result in desired emergent properties at a collective level is notoriously difficult.

COLMENA is a novel approach to develop and orchestrate services across the Continuum. On the one hand, the decomposition of the service into several roles extends the actor model adapting it to the Compute Continuum by enabling the scaling of the number of instances of each role. On the other hand, COLMENA proposes a novel mechanism for orchestration where devices autonomously decide the role assignments based on QoS metrics. There already exist a myriad of frameworks to measure different metrics – e.g., Scaphandre for energy consumption –, extract and standardize them – e.g., OpenTelemetry – and aggregate them for archival or real-time analysis – Prometheus. COLMENA can incorporate some of these frameworks for capturing the metrics that are relevant for both the infrastructure and the operation of services.

3. Pilot use case: Video surveillance

To provide a practical context for evaluating the capabilities of COLMENA, we introduce a pilot use case centred on a video surveillance system, which is relevant in a variety of domains, including road and traffic management, detection of missing people, and security [26].

While COLMENA is designed to support a broad range of applications, this use case offers a tangible, relatable scenario to assess key functionalities such as autonomous role management, QoS enforcement and scoped communications. Additionally, this use case serves as a consistent narrative throughout the paper, guiding readers through the framework’s concepts and its implementation and evaluation.

The envisioned use case focuses on a company operating across several buildings, some of which have multiple floors subdivided into rooms equipped with cameras. The company seeks to deploy a hyper-distributed application to identify potential intruders entering the

premises by processing images captured by cameras installed in all the lobbies of these buildings. Figure 1 illustrates the infrastructure expected to be used in this example highlighting the cameras whose images should be processed (i.e., in blue, the cameras located at the lobby of each floor).

Figure 1: Infrastructure of the video surveillance use case highlighting the cameras whose images should be processed

The installed cameras, constrained by limited computational capacity, cannot execute the computer vision algorithms necessary for intrusion detection. Consequently, the image processing workload must be offloaded to computing nodes with sufficient resources. In this use case, the computing nodes are servers located in a centralized data processing center (DPC) at the company’s headquarters. However, the infrastructure could also leverage edge servers in smaller DPCs in each company building or even virtual instances hosted in the cloud.

Quick processing of captured images is crucial in the described use case due to the real-time nature of intrusion detection. Especially, during periods of increased activity, like peak entry/exit hours, prolonged processing times could result in a backlog of images, leading to degraded system performance and an inability to respond swiftly to threats. Establishing a threshold for the Quality of Service allows the system to adapt the amount of allocated resources to fluctuating workloads while maintaining operational efficiency and responsiveness.

4. The COLMENA framework

As outlined in the [Introduction](#) section, COLMENA is designed to support all stakeholders involved in hyper-distributed applications by addressing issues in

every phase of their life-cycle: construction, deployment, and operation. During the construction phase, it aims at simplifying the coding process for Developers. At the deployment stage, it assists Providers in instantiating services on infrastructure owned by one or more Infrastructure Owners to whom it provides tools to control the usage of their devices. In the operation phase, COLMENA offers Providers mechanisms to monitor and manage the application behavior—including the possibility of deploying the continuous software updates facilitated by the Maintainers—and delivers to End-Users a highly secure, reliable, and available solution tailored to their needs.

COLMENA is built around the concept of a unified platform that integrates a vast, heterogeneous set of IoT devices, smart systems, edge servers, and Cloud platforms, collectively forming a Compute Continuum. The platform design draws inspiration from successful examples of natural systems, such as organic colonies, where each member autonomously determines its contributions to the community based on its capabilities and the needs of the community by playing specific roles. Similarly, in COLMENA, devices within an IT infrastructure act as Autonomous AgeNTs (ANTs). These ANTs leverage their individual capabilities and contextual awareness to decide how best to contribute to the overall system’s objectives. The ANTs self-organize to establish a decentralized mesh architecture that supports multiple collaboration mechanisms: peer-to-peer communication, data and software sharing, and exchanging serverless computation.

In this analogy, developing a service for such a platform resembles designing the "society" formed by these individuals. Specifically, it involves defining the roles composing the society (functionalities in the system), specifying their associated behaviors, and detailing the skills and capabilities (both hardware and software) required to carry out each role effectively.

Optimally distributing functionalities across the Compute Continuum remains a significant challenge in deploying hyper-distributed services. The challenge arises due to the difficulty of managing a vast scale infrastructure. The complexity of the problem grows when considering the heterogeneity of the system. Furthermore, the dynamic nature of networks and the variability in workloads complicates establishing and applying general rules to simplify the problem. This requires continuous evaluation and re-adaptation. Currently, services are typically deployed using static, and often sub-optimal, strategies or rely on resource-intensive centralized solutions.

In contrast, we propose leveraging the autonomy of

devices and embracing a fully decentralized approach that gives these devices the freedom to fail. Within this paradigm, each ANT autonomously determines which roles it is best suited to execute, based on the capabilities of the ANT and the current needs of the services. To enable ANTs to evaluate their performance and contribution when running a role and assess the overall quality of service (QoS) and experience (QoE) being delivered, a set of key performance indicators (KPIs) and their expected values must be defined. These KPIs allow devices to identify the specific needs and surpluses of each functionality within the system.

Using these indicators, COLMENA agents autonomously select roles that align with their capabilities and context, aiming to contribute to an optimal distribution of functionalities. This self-organizing approach reduces dependency on centralized coordination, improves adaptability to dynamic conditions, and facilitates efficient resource utilization across the Continuum.

4.1. Software stack

To construct and operate services on such a platform, we propose (and implement as described in section 6) the four-layer software architecture shown in Figure 2. At its foundation (layer 0), there are the **IT resources** that compose the underlying infrastructure. These can be either individual hardware nodes such as single board computers, edge servers, robots, virtual instances; virtual machines and containers; or whole virtualization platforms, Clouds and Container-as-a-Service clusters (e.g., Kubernetes or K3s).

This base layer reflects the heterogeneity inherent in the system, encompassing variations in available network interfaces, computing resources, smart systems (sensors and actuators), and storage capabilities. Such diversity in infrastructure components highlights the need for a flexible and adaptable software stack to unify and effectively use these resources across the Continuum.

The first software layer, **ANT Handler**, transforms each IT device into an interoperable ANT, ensuring an efficient operation by tailoring its functionality to the specific compute, network, storage, and sensing/actuating capabilities of the device and their current availability. The *ANT Monitor* component gathers and monitors information about the ANT’s capabilities and their usage, providing a real-time understanding of the device’s operational state. The *Role Optimiser* focuses on maximising resource utilisation, performance, and energy efficiency adapting the execution of roles to align with the specific hardware capabilities of the device. The *Communication Controller* monitors the current

Figure 2: COLMENA framework software stack

network conditions to dynamically establish communication channels that meet specific requirements such as latency, bandwidth, and reliability. The *Smart System Controller* provides a generic interface to interact securely and remotely with the embedded sensors and actuators, facilitating seamless integration with the physical environment. Designed for Infrastructure Owners, the *ANT Configuration Manager* provides a mechanism to restrict the software to run on the device, the access to its smart systems, the amount of shared computational and storage resources and its electric power consumption. All these components are deployed on each device and operate locally without requiring external interaction with other ANTs.

The second layer establishes a collaboration plane among ANTs, transforming the infrastructure into a cohesive **Swarm Platform** rather than merely a collection of heterogeneous devices. While all components of this layer are deployed in each ANT, its components work cooperatively with their counterparts in other devices

to achieve collective goals and ensure seamless operation. The *Context Manager* equips ANTs with comprehensive context awareness. It integrates self-context information, such as capacities (via the ANT Monitor), identity, location, and ownership, with environment-context information, including the capabilities, proximity, volatility, and trustworthiness of neighboring ANTs. The *Sharing Manager* facilitates seamless cooperation among ANTs by establishing mechanisms to share software images, data and even computational workload seamlessly across the continuum. Additionally, this component becomes an interface to enable external interaction offering a unified and cohesive view of the Swarm platform, thus simplifying operations over the platform as a whole. The *Distributed Service Manager* is responsible for selecting which roles to be hosted locally aiming to contribute to the overall service performance. To achieve this purpose it includes a QoE & QoS Assessment module that evaluates the status of the QoS/QoE metrics defined by the Developer as KPIs.

Figure 3: Deployment model of the components of the software stack

This information is fed into the Role Selection module, which uses decision-making policies to determine the number of instances of each role to be played by the device, considering its current conditions and owner preferences. Continuously reconsidering this decision allows a dynamic adaptation of the deployment delivering an agile, robust and efficient platform. Section [Decision-making policies](#) details the initial policies implemented in the prototype version of the Role Selection module.

The **Service Tools** layer provides a suite of tools to support service stakeholders relying on the Swarm. These tools do not necessarily run on an ANT of the swarm; they can run on any device with access to the platform. The layer offers three tools designed to assist Developers in implementing and maintaining the service. The *Swarm Programming Model* allows the description of a service as a composite of different roles indicating their requirements and establishing their KPIs. *Role Operation Abstractions* streamline the development of role behaviors by providing generic interfaces to communicate, share data, interact with smart systems, and distribute the computational load of the role. Finally, the layer offers the *Swarm Intelligence library* that facilitates the development of intelligent services by incorporating continuous learning and Swarm Intelligence algorithms.

At the end of the construction phase, Developers generate a software bundle that includes a description of the service, all the source code and necessary configuration files. This package is then delivered to the Service Providers, who use the *Service Deployment Tool* to instantiate the service. This tool processes the bundle

to generate all necessary software images for running the service, such as role-specific images. Leveraging the Sharing Manager within the Swarm Platform layer, the tool publishes these generated images to the shared software repository and propagates the service description across the platform to enable its deployment. Following the publication of the service description, ANTs autonomously determine which roles to execute.

During the operational phase, the *Service Operation Dashboard* enables Service Providers to monitor and manage deployed services. This dashboard supports continuous service improvements by facilitating software updates, thereby integrating a Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) methodology into the service life-cycle.

The topmost layer of the stack comprises those **Services** relying on the platform to deliver solutions characterized by exceptionally high availability, reliability, and trustworthiness to End-Users. These services are the ultimate beneficiaries of the platform's robust and adaptive architecture, ensuring seamless operation and responsiveness to dynamic demands while maintaining the highest standards of performance and security.

To ensure secure service execution and facilitate software management, COLMENA employs virtual environments and containerization technologies like Docker or Balena. Figure 3 illustrates the deployment of the components of the software stack. Each ANT operates a dedicated container, referred to as the COLMENA Agent, which encompasses the two lowest layers of the architecture for handling the underlying resources, providing efficient performance and supporting all the collaboration mechanisms. Service roles are executed

within individual containers, each containing the specific logic for their behavior alongside the implementation of the Role Operation Abstractions which interact with the components of the COLMENA Agent, promoting modularity, adaptability, and efficient integration.

4.2. Programming model

The COLMENA Programming Model is designed to simplify the development of hyper-distributed applications by providing a clear framework for defining services and their roles, along with the performance indicators (KPIs) that will drive their deployment across the network of devices (ANTs). The model enables developers to break down services into modular, interacting roles, each with specific behaviors and responsibilities. Throughout this section, the use case described in Section [Pilot use case: Video surveillance](#) will be used to illustrate the application of the model, as demonstrated by the code snippet in Listing 1.

In COLMENA, a service represents the overall structure of a hyper-distributed application and is defined by extending the `Service` class. Roles are the building blocks of these services and represent individual functionalities. These are implemented as inner classes of the `Service` extending the `Role` class. Using decorators on the constructor method of the service, developers specify which cooperation components are required for the service’s functionality. These decorators can define shared data spaces and communication channels for roles within the service, facilitating smooth cooperation between different instances of the roles. The `@Data` decorator designates a shared data space, and the `@Channel` decorator sets up communication channels to facilitate message passing between role instances.

For roles to access a shared data space or publish/receive messages from a channel, developers have to decorate the constructor method of the role to indicate that it uses them. Within each role, the `behavior` method implements the core logic of the role and defines the actions it will perform. The behavior of a role can either be continuously running a specific task (Persistent roles), like reading a sensor or streaming data, or being triggered asynchronously reacting to events (Asynchronous roles) — such as messages received through one of the communication channels. To indicate the type of role, developers annotate the behavior function with the `@Persistent` decorator for the continuous roles, while the `@Async` decorator marks roles that should execute in response to incoming messages, specifying which message channel triggers the role’s behavior.

In the example, the video surveillance service (defined in line 1) declares two roles, `Sensing` (line 9) and

`Processing` (line 23). These roles rely on a communication channel named `pending_images` (declared in line 4). The `Sensing` role uses the `pending_images` channel (line 12) to continuously (line 17) publish images captured by the camera. The `Processing` role also uses the `pending_images` channel (line 25) but executes its behavior asynchronously whenever an image is retrieved from the channel (line 31), applying a computer vision algorithm to the image.

```

1 class VideoSurveillance(Service):
2
3     @Context("premises", class=Premises)
4     @Channel("pending_images", scope="")
5     @Metric("processing_time")
6     def __init__(self, *args, **kwargs):
7         pass
8
9     class Sensing(Role):
10        @Requirements("/devices/camera")
11        @Context("premises", scope="*/lobby")
12        @Channel("pending_images")
13        @KPI("num_players = 1")
14        def __init__(self, *arg, **kwarg):
15            # Initialize the role
16
17        @Persistent()
18        def behavior(self):
19            image = # Get image from camera
20            time = time.time()
21            self.pending_images.publish([time, image])
22
23    class Processing(Role):
24        @Requirements("/processor/GPU")
25        @Channel("pending_images")
26        @Metric("processing_time")
27        @KPI("processing_time[2s] < 3")
28        def __init__(self, *arg, **kwarg):
29            # Initialize the role
30
31        @Async(message="pending_images")
32        def behavior(self, message):
33            t_capture = message[0]
34            image = message[1]
35            process_image(image)
36            t_processed = time.time()
37            delay = t_processed - t_capture
38            self.processing_time.publish(delay)
39
40        def process_image(self, image):
41            # Call Computer Vision Library
42            # Returns processing time
43
44    class Premises(Context):
45        def __init__(self, *args, **kwargs):
46            super().__init__(*args, **kwargs)
47
48        def locate(self, device):
49            # Obtain the corresponding location using
50            # devices configuration and sensor data.
51            # location = "Headquarters.floor2.lobby"
52            return location

```

Listing 1: Implementation of the video surveillance use case

In addition to defining the role’s behavior, developers can also specify the hardware and software requirements needed for a role to function properly. These requirements are automatically taken into account by ANTs when deciding which roles to run. The `@Requirements` decorator on a role constructor sets

constraints on the hardware and software a device must possess to host the role execution. For example, the `Sensing` role specifies that the host device must be equipped with a camera (line 10); and the `Processing` role requires a GPU (line 24).

A critical factor for effectively deploying a hyper-distributed application in the Compute Continuum is the contextual circumstances of each device. Attributes such as the geographical region (e.g., country or city), precise GPS coordinates, or the ownership of the device can significantly influence the deployment strategy. To address this, COLMENA encapsulates a specific situational attribute of the devices within the `Context` concept. Rather than relying solely on predefined contexts, COLMENA enables the definition of custom contextual circumstances by extending the `Context` class. This involves implementing the `locate` method to determine the device's current classification based on its configuration and sensor data.

This approach provides COLMENA with the flexibility to tailor contextual definitions to the unique needs of each application. Using the `@Context` decorator on the constructor method of a role, developers can restrict the deployment of the role to those ANTs that currently meet that circumstantial aspect. For example, the video surveillance use case defines a new `Context` to describe the location of the devices within the company premises (line 44). For controlling people entering the company buildings, only those devices in any of the lobbies within the premises are needed to host the `Sensing` role (line 11). While the example demonstrates the use of a single context to constrain the deployment of a role to specific circumstances, COLMENA supports more complex conditions that combine multiple contexts. For example, deployment criteria could simultaneously require devices to be located in the lobby, manufactured by ACME Inc., and owned by the company.

In addition to restricting the deployment of roles, contexts can also limit the scope of role cooperation and facilitate the creation of multiple shared data spaces or communication channels tailored to specific cooperation environments. Developers can specify the sharing scope by setting the `scope` parameter in the `@Data` and `@Channel` decorators on the service constructor. The video surveillance example only establishes one single communication channel for the whole system (line 4); however, other services using the same context may need to establish a communication channel for each floor or keep a private instance for a piece of data in each ANT.

Quality of Experience (QoE), Quality of Service (QoS), and performance indicators play a crucial role

in determining the instantiation of roles within COLMENA. By annotating the constructor method of a role with `@KPI`, specific conditions can be set to evaluate whether the execution of the role is necessary or not. These conditions rely on metrics that are collected dynamically during runtime. COLMENA collects some predefined metrics which are broadly applicable to most of the services; for instance, the number of devices currently playing a specific role. In addition, application-specific metrics can be introduced by annotating the service constructor with the `@Metric` decorator specifying the name of the metric. The responsibility for managing these custom metrics relies entirely on the application logic; their roles, also annotated with the `@Metric` decorator with a matching name, must explicitly expose their values to ensure proper integration.

Often, the conditions defined by a KPI are not concerned with the global, instantaneous value of a metric but instead rely on an aggregated value over a specific timeframe. For example, the aggregated metric over the last five seconds of operation may be more relevant for decision-making. Similarly, KPIs may also impose constraints based on a given contextual scope. For instance, they can limit the number of devices running the role belonging to the same owner or monitor the amount of workload pending to be processed in the building where the ANT is located to adjust the number of nodes playing the role processing it locally. The `@KPI` decorator accepts expressions following the pattern `MetricName("ContextName"="scope") [timeframe]` enabling developers to specify both the desired timeframe and the contextual scope of the metric.

The pilot use case introduces a custom metric (line 5), `processing_time`, to measure the time required to process each image. This metric enables dynamic role deployment by providing a feedback loop based on performance. The `Sensing` role contributes to this metric by adding a timestamp to each captured image before publishing it to the `pending_images` channel. The `Processing` role calculates and exposes the `processing_time` metric (lines 38); since the behavior of the role explicitly needs the metric, it is required to annotate also the role construction with the `@Metric` decorator (line 26).

The deployment of the `Processing` role is governed by a `@KPI` condition relying on this custom metric. Specifically, the KPI requires the average value of `processing_time` during the last two seconds to remain below three seconds. If this threshold is exceeded, additional instances of the `Processing` role should be instantiated on suitable ANTs. Figure 4 illustrates how

the various elements discussed throughout this section — context, cooperation mechanisms, metrics, and KPIs — integrate seamlessly within the COLMENA framework to implement the video surveillance use case.

Figure 4: Video surveillance pilot architecture

4.3. Decision-making policies

As introduced in the [Software stack](#) Section, COLMENA agents monitor services through the QoE & QoS assessment component of the distributed service manager. This component tracks the current values for the KPIs defined by Developers through the programming model. The role selector component leverages the information provided by this QoE & QoS assessment component and implements decision-making policies to start and terminate the execution of roles depending on the agent’s contribution to QoS compliance. This section describes decision-making policies considered for implementing the role selector.

Reinforcement Learning (RL) algorithms are well-suited for role selection due to their ability to dynamically adapt through repeated interactions with the environment. By maximizing the cumulative reward, agents learn optimal policies for starting and stopping roles within the deployed service. Furthermore, the extension of RL to Multi-Agent RL (MARL) — by adding coordination between agents and game theory [27] — aligns with the decentralized nature offered by the COLMENA platform.

At each step, an agent selects an action and subsequently receives a numerical reward signal that reflects the impact of the action on the environment. The learning process involves balancing exploration of new actions and exploitation of known, high-reward actions, with the policy being periodically updated to reflect the agent’s improved understanding of the environment.

Q-Learning [28] and SARSA [29] are two well-known algorithms reducing the multi-agent problem to a single-agent problem, which is referred to as independent learning. Another consideration is to use an interconnected learning automata (LA), which is a MARL algorithm based on policy iteration of multiple LA, a gradient ascend approach [30]. Besides RL, rule-based approaches, which rely on simple predefined rules for starting and stopping roles, have been widely used for handling QoS and QoE. Rule-based implementations are deterministic and simple; therefore, they are alternatives particularly well-suited for devices with constrained resources.

4.3.1. Q-Learning and SARSA

Temporal-difference learning (TD) encompasses a family of RL algorithms that learn action-value functions through repeated interaction with the environment.

Each action a^t performed at a given state s^t is associated with a Q value, denoted as $Q(s^t, a^t)$. The agent maintains Q values of all state-action pairs, representing estimates of the cumulative rewards obtainable from those states and actions. States refer to representations of the environment and are part of the theoretical formulation of Markov Decision Processes, used in RL. At each iteration, the agent updates the Q value for the current state-action pair, $Q(s^t, a^t)$, using the new information gathered from the environment.

Q-Learning and SARSA are specific algorithms within the TD learning category of methods. In Q-Learning, the update rule is given by:

$$Q(s^t, a^t) \leftarrow Q(s^t, a^t) + \alpha \left[r^t + \gamma \max_{a' \in A} Q(s^{t+1}, a') - Q(s^t, a^t) \right] \quad (1)$$

In SARSA, the update rule is:

$$Q(s^t, a^t) \leftarrow Q(s^t, a^t) + \alpha \left[r^t + \gamma Q(s^{t+1}, a^{t+1}) - Q(s^t, a^t) \right] \quad (2)$$

In both algorithms, α is the learning rate and γ adjusts the weight of the future state. Higher values of γ place more emphasis on long-term planning, while small values prioritize immediate rewards. While SARSA updates the Q values using the action actually taken at time $t + 1$ following the agent’s current policy, Q-learning uses the maximum possible Q value for the next state.

TD learning is combined traditionally with an ϵ -greedy policy to find a balance between exploration and exploitation. In this policy, ϵ is the probability that an

agent selects a random action. Conversely, with probability $1-\epsilon$, the agent selects the maximum Q value for the current state.

Exploration allows agents to try out new actions or strategies to gather more information about the environment, while exploitation leverages the existing knowledge to select actions that optimize the reward.

4.3.2. Interconnected Learning Automaton

LAs [31] are policy iterators that keep a probability associated to each action, they are also called gradient ascent approaches. Similarly, as in other RL methods, the probabilities are updated based on feedback from the environment. Unlike TD learning, LAs select the action directly by sampling the probability distribution. Once an action a_i is taken, the update rule is:

$$p_{a_i}(t+1) = p_{a_i}(t) + \lambda_1 r(t)(1 - p_{a_i}(t)) - \lambda_2(1 - r(t))p_{a_i}(t) \quad (3)$$

λ_1 and λ_2 are the reward and penalty parameters. The non-chosen actions (i.e., a_j) are also updated, using the following formula:

$$p_{a_j}(t+1) = p_{a_j}(t) - \lambda_1 r(t)p_{a_j}(t) + \lambda_2(1 - r(t))\left(\frac{1}{K-1} - p_{a_j}(t)\right) \quad (4)$$

K is the total number of actions. Interconnected LA [32] consists of applying one LA in each state of the system, such that only one automaton is active at each time point. The active automaton is updated with an estimate of the average reward, which is calculated by dividing the accumulated reward by the total elapsed time since the last visit to the state.

4.3.3. Rule-Based policy

Besides RL algorithms, rule-based algorithms can be beneficial because of their simplicity. We have implemented an approach where some roles are always active (Eager), and others are only activated when the KPI is not fulfilled (Lazy). For Lazy roles to stop running, they can be associated with an internal metric that determines how much they are contributing to the QoS (such as the number of executions).

5. Evaluation of decision-making policies

This section evaluates the collective behavior that emerges in the pilot use case when COLMENA manages the underlying swarm by applying the proposed

policies. To support this evaluation, we developed a dedicated simulator whose goal is not to model the performance, network and resource usage, or energy consumption of a concrete deployment, but to validate the emergence and stability of collective behaviors induced by role selection policies within the COLMENA framework.

In this simulator, implemented in Java, each ANT is modeled as an independent thread, enabling the representation of autonomous and concurrent behavior. Each ANT maintains its own monitoring and decision-making components, including an ANT Monitor, which tracks the availability and usage of local hardware resources; a Context Manager, which observes and propagates changes in the ANT's contextual conditions; and a Service Manager, which governs role selection and adaptation decisions. Users specify the number of devices in the simulation, define their resource characteristics, and set their initial contextual conditions programmatically; they can also modify these parameters dynamically during the simulation.

To support interaction among ANTs, the simulator relies on shared memory to represent communication and data sharing mechanisms in a simplified yet effective manner. Both communication channels and data sharing mechanisms are context-aware, allowing their behavior to adapt based on the current state of the ANT. Communication channels are modeled as queues, while shared data are managed through a Data Manager static class. This design allows the simulator to capture the effects of coordination and information sharing among ANTs without introducing unnecessary complexity related to distributed communication protocols.

Metric management follows a similar approach to data sharing, while being specialized for system observation and evaluation. Each ANT produces and publishes contextualized metrics that reflect its local state and behavior. The simulator collect these metrics, automatically aggregates them according to the contextualized KPIs queries currently registered, and publishes both local and aggregated values into a time-series database. By handling aggregation and storage transparently, the simulator reduces the individual burden on ANTs and facilitates the evaluation of policy impact on collective performance over time.

Each ANT's thread manages the status of its associated devices by processing actions on a deadline basis. Every action—such as initializing the COLMENA framework, completing setup, instantiating a policy, executing a policy, or finalizing a policy—has an associated resource consumption profile. When an action is executed, it reserves and releases the required resources,

publishes the corresponding metrics, and produces a specific impact on the system. As part of this impact, actions can enqueue subsequent actions; for example, starting a policy automatically schedules the action corresponding to its completion. In the case of cyclic actions, it is the responsibility of the action itself to enqueue the next phase of the cycle with the appropriate deadline.

The simulator also allows defining services, their associated roles, shared object and channels, and KPIs metrics following the programming model. At any point during a simulation, users can trigger the deployment of a new service, which will be considered by each ANT’s Service Manager in the next policy evaluation cycle. For each role, it is possible to specify its type – persistent or asynchronous – as well as the resources consumed during idle and active states, and the impact of each associated action.

In the video surveillance use case, two roles are defined: Sensing and Processing. Camera agents perform the Sensing role by periodically adding images to a shared image queue, while GPU agents execute the Processing role by retrieving and processing these images. The queue serves as the central communication mechanism between the roles.

Experiments were configured with two agents equipped with a camera and varying the number of agents with a GPU depending on the experiment. Agents with a camera are configured with an Eager policy; therefore, two Sensing roles will always be active. Conversely, Agents with a GPU will activate/deactivate roles according to the decision-making engine.

5.1. Policies configuration

We configured the policies introduced in [Decision-making policies](#) and evaluated them using the simulator.

For TD learning algorithms, we use a learning rate of $\alpha = 0.1$ and $\gamma = 0.99$. We have chosen a rather large learning rate so that the system can quickly learn in the presence of events, but still considered a high γ to balance immediate and future rewards. The system operates in two states: KPI met and KPI not met.

The reward function is based on the difference between the current and previous KPI values, as well as whether the KPI is above a defined threshold (which indicates whether the KPI is met). As seen in Equation 5, a high reward is given when the KPI value $v(t)$ is within a desired range (close below the KPI threshold), while rewards become negative as the KPI moves further from this range. The reward becomes positive if the KPI value moves closer to the range. Value η_1 and

η_2 are used for scaling the reward (we used 5.0 and 0.25, respectively, which we found by fine tuning).

$$r(t) = \begin{cases} \eta_1, & \text{if } 0.5 < v(t) < 0.9, \\ \frac{v(t)-v(t-1)}{\eta_2 T}, & \text{if } v(t) < 0.5 \text{ or } (0.9 < v(t) < T), \\ \frac{-v(t)+v(t-1)}{\eta_2 T}, & \text{if } v(t) > T. \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

The system balances exploration and exploitation with an initial exploration rate ($\epsilon = 0.5$), which decreases gradually ($\delta_\epsilon = 0.005$) down to a minimum of ($\epsilon = 0.001$). After the initial exploration period is finalized, we apply the Boltzmann adaptive approach [33] with parameters $\delta = 0.1$, $\sigma = 2.0$, and $\epsilon_{max} = 0.4$. We used this approach because it is commonly used in the literature for dynamically adjusting the exploration to the environment, which is particularly important for agents to react under events or changing conditions. We manually adjusted these values so that ϵ substantially increases when the KPI was out of the desired range. However, if ϵ is too large, the randomness does not allow the system to learn under the presence of an event.

For the interconnected LA policy, we use two automata, one for each state. Both automata share the same parameters: $\lambda_1 = 0.3$ and $\lambda_2 = 0.005$. To calculate the average reward, a discount parameter is applied to weight immediate rewards by 0.4, ensuring a balance between short-term and long-term objectives. The high reward parameter, λ_1 , emphasizes positive rewards, encouraging desirable outcomes, while the smaller penalty parameter, λ_2 , minimises penalty (which is applied to all rewards smaller than 1).

Additionally, λ_2 prevents the probabilities from converging to extremes (0 or 1), thereby promoting exploration. This incentivizes the system to remain adaptable in dynamic environments, allowing it to respond to changing conditions. Feedback is calculated by comparing the current KPI value to its previous value. A feedback score ranging from -1 to 1 is assigned based on whether the current value is equal to, greater than, or less than the previous value.

5.2. Results

Firstly, the policies for decision-making are compared in Figure 5. To provide a baseline for comparison, we included a Random policy, which assigns equal probabilities to starting and stopping the role. Two cameras were configured to capture images continuously, and four agents with processing capabilities were set to use the same policy. The simulator ran for 10 minutes, and the experiments were repeated six times to measure

Figure 5: Policy evaluation using the Video Surveillance use case, showing the KPI processing time (left) and the number of active processing roles (right). The experiment is repeated six times for five different policies a-e.

variability. This process was repeated for each policy. The plots show the values of the KPI *Processing time*, including the mean and 95% confidence intervals over the experiments (left), as well as the number of active processing roles throughout the simulation (right).

The Random policy (Figure 5a) has an average of 1.98 active roles, approximately half of the available agents, and the KPI evolution shows that this policy does not meet QoS requirements (the red line indicates the 3 seconds threshold). The other policies stay below the threshold for most of the simulation. The Rule-Based policy (Figure 5b) shows the lowest KPI mean; however, it also has a higher mean number of active roles (2.84) compared to SARSA (2.29), Q-Learning (2.29), and LA (2.40)—Figure 5c-5e. This behavior explains that the Rule-Based policy is not designed to optimize the use of available resources. Finally, the LA policy exhibits greater variability than Q-Learning and SARSA because the exploration-exploitation balance is better controlled in the two latter, as they employ the ϵ -greedy adaptive exploration mechanism only when the KPI is outside the desired range.

In Figure 6, the number of available processing agents is increased from 4 to 6, 8, and 10. In this case, the plot displays the mean of active processing roles over the total runtime, along with the 95% confidence interval. The variability of the plot reflects changes in the number of active roles during the experiments.

The Random policy consistently uses half the avail-

Figure 6: Scalability test using the Video Surveillance use case. The experiment is repeated for each policy and with 4, 6, 8, and 10 agents, three times each during 10 minutes. It shows the average value and 95% confidence interval of the number of active processing roles throughout the experiment.

able agents (2, 3, 4, and 5), while other policies find solutions using fewer resources. SARSA performs best, with consistent values across configurations (e.g., 2.29, 2.30, 2.32, and 2.55). LA policy does not scale as well as the RL counterparts, with values 2.40, 2.50, 2.95, and 3.63. One explanation for the poorer scaling of LA is that the randomness inherent in the algorithm is harder to control than in the other methods. For systems with more than 10 agents, convergence to an optimal solution becomes increasingly difficult, particularly with no coordination between agents. As noted in [27], even with deep learning-based MARL algorithms, typical experiments use between 2 and 10 agents.

Figure 7: Policy evaluation using the Video Surveillance use case, showing the KPI processing time (left) and the number of active processing roles (right). At $t = 300s$, a new camera starts. The experiment is repeated six times for five different policies a-e.

Finally, Figure 7 analyzes the system’s behavior under the presence of a dynamicity event. At ($t = 300s$), a new device equipped with a camera joins the system. For this experiment we use 5 agents with processing roles, so that they are able to react to the event.

This situation introduces a significant challenge for RL methods, as the exploration-exploitation trade-off becomes more complex. The system must find a new balance for this changed environment by forgetting the previous Q-values and updating them to fit the new scenario. The results show that all policies, except the Random policy, adjust their number of active roles, trending closer to 4. Since there are more available processing agents than before, the KPI is below the threshold in the first part of the experiment for the Random policy too. However, when one camera is added, the system shows a similar trend as before.

Q-Learning and SARSA do not fully converge to KPI values below the threshold, although they stay close to it. In contrast, the LA policy exhibits a higher peak initially but ultimately discovers a better solution than the RL counterparts, albeit with greater variance. The Rule-Based policy adapts well to the environmental change, but with higher cost value.

This evaluation shows that the rule-based approach works best under the three experiments, even though it is more tailored to the use case. This means that the Developer has to specify one KPI to act on, and therefore has to know in advance that running the role will im-

prove the QoS. For some indicators, this might not be the case. Instead, RL algorithms dynamically discover how running roles affect KPI values. In the first and second experiments, the three RL algorithms perform well, with SARSA and Q-Learning having less variance. However, the LA approach exhibits a slightly better adaptation to changes than SARSA and Q-Learning, but with a higher variance. This could be improved by adding better dynamicity to the algorithm, for example by improving exploration-exploitation under the presence of events or adding coordination between agents.

6. Prototype implementation and evaluation

This section evaluates a prototype implementation of COLMENA using the video-surveillance use. The objective of the section is to assess the practical feasibility of the proposed framework and to analyze its behavior under realistic execution conditions. To this end, we developed a functional prototype that implements the most of the COLMENA software stack described in [The COLMENA framework](#) (released as open-source software and publicly available at <https://github.com/colmena-swarm>) and deployed the video-surveillance service on a real testbed composed of heterogeneous devices.

The prototype is built by integrating a set of existing technologies that support communication, observability, virtualization, and workload distribution across hetero-

geneous devices. Zenoh is used as the core communication substrate, enabling both inter-ANT communication and data sharing among roles. The observability infrastructure also relies on Zenoh for publishing metric values, while Prometheus is used to store and monitor these metrics to support QoS and QoE assessment. In addition, node-exporter is employed to collect information about available hardware resources and their utilization on each device. Application components are virtualized using Docker, which allows services and roles to be deployed consistently across the platform. At present, Docker Hub is used as the software repository; however, alternative distribution mechanisms based on BitTorrent and IPFS have also been explored. The Context Manager is implemented as a microservice that periodically executes Docker images corresponding to the contexts defined by deployed services and notifies other components to react to contextual changes. Finally, COMPSs—one of the solutions considered in the related work [6]—is integrated to enable roles to distribute their workload dynamically across the system.

The video surveillance service is developed using the swarm programming model as shown in (Listing 1) and a package with the service description and all the necessary files for creating the images is created. The service is deployed on the testbed using the service deployment tool, which creates a Docker image for each role and context, uploads them to the software repository (Docker Hub) and an updated service description referencing the uploaded images is published to the Zenoh network, to be received by all COLMENA Agents currently composing the swarm.

The video-surveillance service is developed using the swarm programming model, as illustrated in Listing 1. With it, the programming model creates the package containing the service description and all necessary files for building the Docker images. Deployment on the testbed is performed using the service deployment tool, which generates multi-arch – linux/arm64 and linux/amd64 – Docker images for each role and context, uploads these images to the software repository (Docker Hub), and publishes an updated service description referencing the uploaded images to the Zenoh network. This description is then received by all COLMENA Agents currently composing the swarm, enabling them to instantiate the corresponding roles and contexts.

The implementation of the Sensing role publishes an image every second and the image is processed with a simple 2D array sum, adding an additional 0.75 second delay to emulate an actual computer vision workload. Two devices are configured as if they had cameras equipped and the other two devices have enough

computing capacity to process images. A KPI of $\text{avg}(\text{processing_time}[5s]) < 2$ is declared, meaning that the average value of the processing time in the last 5 seconds should be below 2.

We performed an experimental evaluation of the current implementation of COLMENA deploying COLMENA on a testbed composed of four heterogeneous devices: Odroid-H3 (amd64), NVIDIA Jetson TX1 (arm64/v8), Raspberry Pi 4 (arm64/v8), Odroid N2 (arm32/v7). A network that connects all of the devices is created by connecting all of the devices to a switch and creating network interfaces to route traffic to Internet (needed to access Docker Hub). ANTs are configured to use the rule-based role selection policy.

Figure 8 shows the experiment results: the number of active devices (Figure 8a), the number of active roles in (Figure 8b), and the KPI evolution (Figure 8c). At the start of the experiment, a camera and two image processors are started. One processor is sufficient to process the feed generated by the camera and so the agent running on the Raspberry Pi stops running the processing role. A second camera is started before $t = 40s$. Both camera feeds are too much for a single processor to process with and so the processing time starts to increase, eventually crossing the desired KPI threshold. Another agent starts the processing role in response to the KPI not met.

The average latency starts to fall in response to the new processing role. A second spike is observed as both cameras send images to the same processor. Gradually the system settles into a steady state of equally distributing the two camera feeds between the two image processors. After stopping a camera, the remaining camera chooses to send the camera feed to the message processor with the least latency. The other device stops the image processing role after some time when it deems itself not to be contributing although the KPI is met.

This experiment shows that the system is able to react to changes in the observed state of the service. When it is observed to be outside of the desired range then roles are started in response. This does bring the observed state back into the desired range and once this is done then devices attempt to reduce resource consumption if they judge themselves not to be contributing.

7. Conclusions and Future Work

This manuscript introduces COLMENA, a novel framework for developing, deploying, and operating hyper-distributed applications across the Compute Continuum. COLMENA offers a software stack that includes a programming model to describe services as a

Figure 8: Evaluation results of the distributed implementation of COLMENA.

composition of interacting roles (or functionalities) and leverages the lower layers of the stack to transform each device into an autonomous agent aware of its capabilities and current context. To further facilitate the programming, the framework also provides communication and shared data abstractions, enabling seamless cooperation among roles and devices. Unlike existing solutions that rely on centralized orchestration engines or consensus mechanisms, COLMENA adopts a groundbreaking approach based on the "freedom to fail," allowing devices to autonomously select roles based on the current and desired levels of key indicators, such as QoS, performance, or application-specific requirements.

We demonstrated the framework with a pilot use case: a video surveillance system comprising two roles, Sensing and Processing. The use case is implemented using the programming model and evaluated within both a custom-built simulator and a first version of the agent's software stack.

The custom-built simulator mirrors the framework's core architecture. This simulator includes agent mod-

ules such as the service manager, sharing manager, and context manager, and provides an API for developing and evaluating services in a manner consistent with the programming model.

Decision-making policies are crucial in enabling autonomy in agents. In this article, we introduce three RL-based algorithms (SARSA, Q-Learning, and interconnected Learning Automata) and a rule-based algorithm, which are implemented and evaluated in the simulator. Results indicate that agents successfully learn behaviours that converge toward desired QoS levels in typical environments. However, our experiments revealed challenges for some algorithms in dynamic environments. Future work will focus on enhancing adaptability by incorporating cooperation mechanisms common in multi-agent RL and exploring multi-objective algorithms that optimise multiple KPIs. Additional policies, such as auction-based mechanisms, will also be investigated. We plan to implement these policies directly within the agent's software stack (within the Role Selector component), to assess their performance in heterogeneous and distributed environments. For example, resource-constrained devices may use lightweight, rule-based algorithms, while more capable devices can leverage complex, AI-driven policies.

Additionally, we have developed an initial version of the COLMENA framework, which is publicly available on GitHub. This release includes foundational components, such as the ANT components, programming model and role abstractions. The video surveillance use case is deployed on a testbed of heterogeneous devices, demonstrating the system's reactivity to dynamic events, such as adding or removing devices, under a rule-based policy. Future work will iterate on the middleware to integrate peer-to-peer solutions for message passing, data management, and compute sharing. We will also expand the architecture to address diverse use cases where COLMENA can create meaningful impacts, including healthcare, renewable energy integration, transportation, logistics, and beyond.

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